

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

How organizational commitment mediates the effect of work-life balance on organizational citizenship behavior

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the role of Organizational Commitment Mediating the Effect of Work-Life Balance on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. This study was carried out at the Denpasar City Land Office. The number of population and sample used is 150 employees, with the saturated sample method where all the population is the sample in this study. The data collection method used is a questionnaire. In this study, the data analysis method used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis based on Partial Least Square (PLS). The results showed that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior and organizational commitment, organizational commitment has a positive effect on work-life balance and is able to mediate partially (complementary partial mediation) on the effect of work-life balance on organizational citizenship behavior. It can be concluded that the stronger the work-life balance, the higher the organizational commitment which results in increased organizational citizenship behavior.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Organizational Commitment; Work-life Balance; Human Resource; OCB

1. Introduction

The success of an organization in achieving its goals cannot be separated from the support of Human Resources (HR) in the organization who carry out their duties based on their job descriptions. Some conditions also require employees to work outside their job description, in order to support the goals of the organization. The phenomenon of employees working outside the job description is called Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Organ (2006) mentions that extra behavioral forms of the role of OCB can be implemented in the form of behavior, namely: Altruism, Courtesy, Conscientiousness, Sportsmanship and Civic Virtue. Altruism, namely the behavior of taking the initiative to help or help colleagues in the organization voluntarily. Courtesy, namely individual behavior that maintains good relations with co-workers in order to avoid disputes between members in the organization. Sportsmanship, namely the willingness of individuals to accept whatever is determined by the organization even in unnatural circumstances. Conscientiousness, namely dedication or high dedication to work and the desire to exceed the standard of achievement in every aspect. Civic virtue, namely individual behavior that shows that the individual has a responsibility to be involved, participate, participate, and care in various activities organized by the organization.

According to Bustomi, Sanusi and Herman (2020) that OCB has a positive and significant effect on employee performance so that it can affect organizational performance. OCB is an attitude of employee behavior that is carried out voluntarily, sincerely, happily without having to be ordered and controlled by the company in providing good service (Organ et al., 2006). OCB is a unique aspect of individual activities at work. Organizations will be successful if employees do not only do their main tasks but also want to do extra tasks such as willing to work together, help each

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other, give advice, participate actively, provide extra services to service users, and want to use their working time effectively (Nugraha and Adnyani, 2018).

A preliminary study was conducted to find out the OCB phenomenon in Denpasar City Land Office employees, a preliminary study of 10 employees showed an average OCB value of 3.78. The average score of the item "accepting the discomfort that occurs in the organization" which is included in the sportsmanship indicator is 2.50. The average score of the item "has concern for the changes that occur in the organization" which is included in the civic virtue indicator is 3.40. The average score of the item "trying to do more than the task that should be done" which is included in the conscientiousness indicator is 3.30. The average score of these items is lower than the average value of OCB (appendix 2). Based on the results of the preliminary study, it can be concluded that OCB displayed by Denpasar City Land Office employees tends to focus more on helping behavior (altruism) and maintaining good relations with colleagues (courtesy). This indicates that OCB is not evenly distributed in each indicator, so further research is needed regarding OCB at the Denpasar City Land Office.

Pratama and Mujiati (2019) state that OCB is often explained using social exchange theory. Based on the perspective of social exchange theory, employees who have been treated well by the organization will provide positive feedback for the organization (Fung et al., 2012). Social exchange theory explains the relationship between individuals and organizations, especially between employees and companies or companies and employees. OCB raised by individuals can be influenced by several factors, one of which is work life balance (Harikaran and Thevanes, 2018). Work-life balance creates a balance between the employee's role in work and the employee's role in the family. This balance will have a positive effect on employee behavior at work in the form of extra behavior, such as helping colleagues, providing important information for the continuity of the organization, voluntarily working outside the main task and other behaviors that help organizational goals (Fiernaningsih, et al., 2019).

Research conducted by Hikmah and Lukito (2021) shows that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on OCB. This means that the higher the application of work-life balance, the OCB will increase. These results are supported by research conducted by May and Salahuddin (2021) which found that work-life balance has a significant positive effect on OCB. In contrast to research conducted by Lavanya and Sree (2021) which shows that work-life balance has a negative and insignificant effect on OCB. This result is supported by Shakir and Siddiqui's research (2018) showing that work-life balance does not have a direct effect on OCB. Based on the results of this study, it shows that there are inconsistencies in research results regarding the effect of work-life balance on OCB so that other variables are needed to act as mediators.

Research Susilawati, et al. (2021), found that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB. This is supported by research conducted by Wilkanandya and Sudarma (2020), this study found that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Organizational commitment is the belief and desire to continue to grow with the organization and survive in the organization (Saraswati and Sulistiyo, 2017).

Liu's research, et al. (2021) who found that there is a positive and significant effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment. This statement is supported by research conducted by Badrianto and Ekhsan (2021) that work-life balance has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment. In contrast to research conducted by Nirmalasari (2018) who found that work-life balance does not have a direct effect on organizational commitment. Research by Asmony, et al., (2018) states that organizational commitment is able to mediate the effect of work-life balance on OCB.

Organizations are increasingly required to improve the positive attitudes and behavior of each member in order to improve individual performance. The results of research conducted by Harikaran and Thevanes (2018). states that improving employee work-life balance positively and significantly contributes to increasing organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) of employees in organizations. These results are also supported by research conducted by Research conducted by May and Salahuddin (2021) this research was conducted on Non-Civil Servants Government Employees at the Kubu Raya Regency Land Office with a total of 39 employees. The results of the study show that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Fajri (2022) found that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Erdianza et al. (2020) found that a good work-life balance positively and significantly contributes to increasing employees in the organization. Research conducted by Heriyadi et al. (2020) stated that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on OCB.

H1: Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior.

Saputri and Helmy (2021) on employees at the Department of Labor and Cooperatives, Small and Medium Enterprises of the Kebumen Regency, totaling 35 people, found that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This result is also supported by the results of Oyewobi et al. (2019) Research conducted by Rini and Indrawati (2019) states that there is a significant relationship with the direction of a positive relationship between work life balance and organizational commitment.

The results of Shabir and Gani's research (2020) show that there is a positive and significant relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment. Work-life balance is an indicator of organizational commitment which means that if an employee has a balance between work life and personal life (work-life balance) then he will be more committed to working in an organizational environment (Asmony, et al., 2018).

H2: Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

Rosyadi and Bayudhigantara's research (2021) found a positive and significant effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment. Helmy and Pratama's research (2021) found that organizational commitment can significantly mediate the effect of work-life balance on OCB. Saputri and Helmy (2021) who found that organizational commitment is able to mediate the effect of work-life balance on OCB.

Research by Wilkanandya and Sudarma (2018), found that work-life balance has no significant effect on OCB, while organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Organizational commitment is able to mediate the effect of work-life balance on OCB. These results are supported by research by Eriyanti and Noekent (2021) at the Office of Education, Youth and Sports in Kudus Regency, with 86 employees who stated that organizational commitment is able to mediate the effect of work-life balance on OCB. The effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment will affect OCB, this means that organizational commitment has a major contribution and is able to mediate between work-life balance and OCB.

H4: Organizational commitment mediates the effect of work-life balance on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

Based on the studies that have been conducted, research was conducted to determine the effect of work-life balance on OCB which is mediated by organizational commitment so that the concepts and interrelationships between the variables to be studied can be explained through the following conceptual framework scheme:

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

This research is an associative causality study using a quantitative approach. Causal associative research aims to examine the influence or relationship between two or more variables and see a causal relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable (Sugiyono, 2019). This study was designed to analyze the role of organizational commitment in mediating the effect of work life balance on organizational citizenship behavior.

2.2. Population and Sample

The population in this study were all employees at the Denpasar City Land Office, totaling 150 people. Data were obtained from the Personnel Section of the Denpasar City Land Office as of January 2022. The Denpasar City Land Office employees who make up the population consist of Civil Servants and Non-Civil Servants Government Employees (PPNPN) of the Denpasar City Land Office. The sample selection was carried out using a non-probability sampling technique with a saturated sampling method. The sample technique is selected by taking all members of the population as a sample.

2.3. Data Collection

The data collection method used in this research is to use questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaire scale is arranged in the form of a statement in the form of a Likert scale. Another data collection method was conducted by interviewing to obtain an overview of the Denpasar City Land Office profile.

2.4. Data Analysis Technique

The data analysis technique used in this study is using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) or a structural equation model based on variance or component-based SEM called Partial Least Square (PLS). Partial Least Square (PLS) is used to determine the complexity of the relationship between latent variables and their indicators.

3. Results

3.1. Inferential Analysis

3.1.1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity can be seen from the correlation between the indicator score and the variable score. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation above 0.70. Evaluation of a measurement model based on outer loading is considered valid if it has a loading factor value above 0.50 and or a t-statistic value above 1.96, which means that the model has convergent validity. The results of convergent validity can be seen in table 1.

Table 1 Convergent Validity

	Outer Loadings	p-values	Information
X1.1	0.771	0.000	Valid
X1.2	0.801	0.000	Valid
X1.3	0.836	0.000	Valid
X1.4	0.879	0.000	Valid
X1.5	0.830	0.000	Valid
X1.6	0.840	0.000	Valid
X1.7	0.818	0.000	Valid
X1.8	0.813	0.000	Valid
X1.9	0.783	0.000	Valid
X1.10	0.817	0.000	Valid

	Outer Loadings	p-values	Information
X1.11	0.784	0.000	Valid
X1.12	0.749	0.000	Valid
Z1.1	0.708	0.000	Valid
Z1.2	0.801	0.000	Valid
Z1.3	0.800	0.000	Valid
Z1.4	0.824	0.000	Valid
Z1.5	0.802	0.000	Valid
Z1.6	0.843	0.000	Valid
Z1.7	0.857	0.000	Valid
Z1.8	0.786	0.000	Valid
Z1.9	0.804	0.000	Valid
Y1.1	0.783	0.000	Valid
Y1.2	0.816	0.000	Valid
Y1.3	0.783	0.000	Valid
Y1.4	0.852	0.000	Valid
Y1.5	0.822	0.000	Valid
Y1.6	0.834	0.000	Valid
Y1.7	0.852	0.000	Valid
Y1.8	0.814	0.000	Valid
Y1.9	0.709	0.000	Valid
Y1.10	0.808	0.000	Valid
Y1.11	0.851	0.000	Valid
Y1.12	0.819	0.000	Valid
Y1.13	0.803	0.000	Valid
Y1.4	0.781	0.000	Valid
Y1.15	0.791	0.000	Valid

Primary Data, 2023

Table 1 shows the results of convergent validity testing of all variable indicators that obtain outer loadings greater than 0.05 and p-values less than 0.05. Thus, all variable indicators in this study are said to be valid or have met the requirements of convergent validity.

3.1.2. Discriminant Validity

One method for assessing discriminant validity is to compare the average variance extracted (\sqrt{AVE}) square root for each variable with a correlation variable between one variable and the other variables in the model. The model has sufficient discriminant variables if the \sqrt{AVE} value for each other variable is greater than the correlation between one variable and the other variables in the model. The following are the results of discriminant validity testing which are shown in table 2.

Table 2 Discriminant Validity

Variable	AVE	\sqrt{AVE}	Correlation		
			Work Life Balance (X1)	Org. Commitment (Z1)	Organization Citizenship Behavior (Y1)
Work Life Balance	0.657	0.811	1.000	0.923	0.881
Org. Commitment	0.646	0.804	0.923	1.000	0.915
Organization Citizenship Behavior	0.654	0.809	0.881	0.915	1.000

Primary Data, 2023

Table 2 shows the results of the discriminant validity test which obtained an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of greater than 0.05 and had a correlation value of each variable that was higher than the correlation between variables. These results indicate that the latent variable indicators themselves are better than other latent variable indicators. So it can be said that the data in this study have met the requirements of discriminant validity.

3.1.3. Composite Reliability

This study tested the reliability with Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability parameters. The results of the reliability test of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability show that the values of all constructs are greater than the minimum limit of Cronbach's Alpha (greater than 0.70) and Composite Reliability (greater than or equal to 0.7). Table 3 shows the Composite Reliability Test Results.

Table 3 Composite Reliability

No.	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
1.	Work Life Balance	0.952	0.958	Reliable
2.	Org. Commitment	0.931	0.942	Reliable
3.	Organization Citizenship Behavior	0.962	0.966	Reliable

Primary Data, 2023

Table 3 shows the test results which obtained Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values for all constructs greater than 0.70. So that all variables in this study have met the requirements of composite reliability.

3.1.4. R-Square

Inner model testing is done by looking at the R-Square value which is the goodness of fit model. The coefficient of determination (R²) is used to assess how much the influence of the endogenous construct is affected by the exogenous construct. An R-square value of 0.75 indicates the model is strong, an R-square value of 0.50 indicates that the model is moderate and an R-square value of 0.25 indicates that the model is weak (Sarstedt et al. 2017). The range of R-square values is 0-1. if the R-square value is close to 0. the weaker the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. conversely if it is close to 1. then the stronger the exogenous influence on endogenous variables. The results of the R-Square test can be seen in Table 4

Table 4 R-Square

Construct	R-square
Org. Commitment	0.851
Organization Citizenship Behavior	0.846

Primary Data, 2023

Table 5.8 shows the R-square value of the Organizational Commitment variable of 0.851. This means that 85.1 percent of the variability of the Organizational Commitment construct can be explained by the Work Life Balance variable. while

the remaining 14.9 percent of the Organizational Commitment variable is explained by other variables outside the model.

Likewise with the Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable which has an R-square value of 0.846. That is, 84.6 percent of the variability of the Organizational Citizenship Behavior construct can be explained by the variables Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment, while the remaining 15.4 percent of the Organizational Citizenship Behavior variables are explained by other variables outside the model.

3.1.5. Predictive-Relevance (Q²)

Inner model testing is done by looking at the Q-square value which is a test for the goodness of fit of the model. If the Q-square value is greater than zero (0) it shows that the model has a predictive relevance value, while the Q-square is less than zero, then it shows that the model lacks predictive relevance. If the calculation results show a Q-square value of more than zero, then the model is said to have appropriate predictive value relevance.

The calculation of the Q-square value can be seen as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - (1 - R_z^2) (1 - R_y^2) \\
 &= 1 - (1 - 0.851^2) (1 - 0.846^2) \\
 Q^2 &= 0.922 = 92.2 \%
 \end{aligned}$$

The Q² value obtained in this study was 0.922 or 92.2 percent, thus it can be concluded that the model in this study has a relevant predictive value because it can explain the information available in this study.

3.2. Hypothesis Testing

3.2.1. Direct Effect

Hypothesis testing is done by testing the two values, namely the p-value is smaller than the alpha value of 5% (0.05) and the t-statistic value must have a value greater than 1.96 (<1.96). Significance values can be obtained using the bootstrapping technique developed by Geisser and Stone. Table 5 shows the direct effect with bootstrapping of the PLS analysis.

Table 5 Direct Effect

Construct	Path Coefficient	T-statistics	p-values	Information
X_Work Life Balance -> Y_Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.246	2.591	0.010	Accepted
X_Work Life Balance -> Z_Org. Commitment	0.923	61.899	0.000	Accepted
Z_Org. Commitment -> Y_Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.687	7.291	0.000	Accepted

Primary Data, 2023

Table 5 shows the results of the direct effect test of each variable. The direct effect of the work life balance variable on organizational citizenship behavior has a t-statistic value of 2.591 > t-table 1.96 and a p-value of 0.010 <0.05, so it can be said that H1 is accepted. The path coefficient value of the work life balance variable on organizational citizenship behavior is 0.246, which means that every increase of one unit of work life balance can increase organizational citizenship behavior by 0.246 assuming the other variables are constant.

The direct effect of the work life balance variable on organizational commitment has a t-statistic value of 61.899 > t-table 1.96 and a p-value of 0.000 <0.05, so it can be said that H2 is accepted. The path coefficient value of the work life balance variable on organizational commitment is 0.923, which means that every increase of one unit of work life balance can increase organizational commitment by 0.923 assuming the other variables are constant.

The direct effect of the organizational commitment variable on organizational citizenship behavior has a t-statistic value of 7.291 > t-table 1.96 and a p-value of 0.000 <0.05, so it can be said that H3 is accepted. The path coefficient value of the organizational commitment variable on organizational citizenship behavior is 0.687, which means that every one

unit increase in organizational commitment can increase organizational citizenship behavior by 0.687 assuming the other variables are constant.

3.2.2. Indirect Effect

Examination of the mediating variable in this study regarding the mediating role of the Organizational Commitment variable on the indirect effect of Work-Life Balance on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The following examination of the indirect effect in this study can be seen in the explanation of the results of the analysis in table 6.

Table 6 Indirect Effect

Variable	Indirect Effect	
	Coefficient Correlation	T-Statistic
X1_Work Life Balance -> Z1_Organizational Commitment -> Y1_Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.634	6.946
Variable	Total Effect	
	Coefficient Correlation	T-Statistic
X1_Work Life Balance -> Y1_Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.881	39.929
X1_Work Life Balance -> Z1_Organizational Commitment	0.923	61.899
Z1_Organizational Commitment -> Y1_Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.687	7.291
VAF -> Indirect Effect/ Total Effect (0.634 / 0.881)	0.730	

Primary Data, 2023

Table 6. shows the role of Organizational Commitment in mediating the effect of work life balance on organizational citizenship behavior with a VAF value of 0.730. This means that the role of organizational commitment as a mediating variable is 73 percent. The mediation value of 73 percent is in the range of 20 percent to 80 percent, so the organizational commitment variable is included in the category of partial mediation variables. So it can be concluded that organizational commitment can partially mediate the effect of work life balance on organizational citizenship behavior.

4. Discussion

4.1. Work-life balance on OCB

The results of the analysis show that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on OCB. These results indicate that the better the work-life balance possessed by employees, the higher the OCB displayed. Based on the results of the study, it is known that the work-life balance of Denpasar City Land Office employees is quite good. There are several problems experienced in balancing personal and work life, such as ignoring personal needs because of work, personal life gets worse because of work, skipping important personal activities because of work, work gets worse because of everything that happens in personal life, personal life drains energy to do work but this can be handled well by most employees. Most employees also stated that their work made them feel better when they were at home and carrying out personal activities. Personal activities carried out will make employees have a better mood at work and feel more relaxed to do work. This shows that even though there are problems originating from work intervention on personal life and personal life on work, most employees are able to balance personal life and work (work-life balance) well.

A good work-life balance owned by Denpasar City Land Office employees will encourage Denpasar City Land Office employees to display OCB as a reciprocal. The OCB that is raised includes helping colleagues who have excessive workload, participating in various organizational activities and trying to do more work than they should do. The work-life balance of Denpasar City Land Office employees will contribute positively and significantly to increasing OCB. These results are in line with several previous studies from Erdianza et al. (2020), Salahuddin (2020), Makiah and Nurmayanti (2018), Harikaran and Thevanes (2018), Iroth et al (2022), Setiadi and Ariefiara (2022), Pratama, et al (2022).

4.2. Work-Life Balance on Organizational Commitment

The results of the analysis show that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This shows that the higher the work-life balance possessed by employees, the higher their organizational commitment will be. The research results are supported by previous research from Saputri and Helmy (2021); Oyewobi et al. (2019) and Liu, et al. (2021). Work-life balance is an indicator of organizational commitment which means that if employees have a good work-life balance, individuals will have a higher commitment to work in an organizational environment (Asmony, et al., 2018). The results of the study show that employees of the Denpasar City Land Office have a fairly good balance between personal life and work (work-life balance). Organizational commitment is also high as shown by employees of the Denpasar City Land Office having a psychological bond by feeling proud to be part of the Denpasar City Land Office, and moral ties and responsibility to be able to work and be loyal to the Denpasar City Land Office. The high organizational commitment possessed by the Denpasar City Land Office occurs as a reciprocity felt by the Denpasar City Land Office Employees for the comfort and support provided by the Denpasar City Land Office to be able to balance personal life and work (work-life balance) properly. These results are also supported by research from Haeruddin, et al (2022) which found that work-life balance has a positive effect on organizational commitment.

4.3. Organizational Commitment on OCB

The results of the analysis show that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB. These results are supported by research from, Susilawati et al. (2021), Nurwadi and Ardana (2019), Purwanto, et al (2021), and Manurung (2021). Organizational commitment can be interpreted as a condition for a person to recognize an organization and organizational goals, as well as their needs so that a desire arises to remain a member of the organization (Sunaris, et al, 2022). Based on the results of the research, employees of the Denpasar City Land Office feel happy spending their career time in the organization, feel proud to be part of the Denpasar City Land Office, have a strong desire to continue working as employees of the Denpasar City Land Office, feel they will bear a loss if they have to leave the organization and feel responsible and must be loyal to work at the Denpasar City Land Office. These results indicate that Denpasar City Land Office employees have high organizational commitment. Extra behavior and efforts made by employees include behavior that exceeds organizational demands and carry out work other than that which is the main task of the position or position held. This work behavior is part of OCB. This can also be seen from the results of the study, namely that most employees of the Denpasar City Land Office stated that they agreed and were willing to help colleagues who had excessive workload (altruism), maintain good relations and avoid disputes with colleagues (courtesy), accept inconvenience and not raising problems that occur in the organization (sportsmanship), Denpasar City Land Office employees also agree to participate in various activities organized by the Denpasar City Land Office (civic virtue), and most employees also agree and try to do more than their duties what should be done (scientiousness). This shows that the higher the organizational commitment, the higher the OCB displayed by the Denpasar City Land Office employees.

4.4. The Role of Organizational Commitment Mediate the Effect of Work-Life Balance on OCB

The results of the analysis show that organizational commitment is able to mediate the effect of work-life balance on OCB. This means that the better the balance between personal and work life (work-life balance) owned by the Land Office employees, the higher the organizational commitment they have which will then have an impact on the higher the displayed OCB frequency. This is also reflected in the results of the study, namely that Land Office employees are able to balance their work-life balance well, which has an impact on their high organizational commitment. This high organizational commitment then influences the frequency of displayed OCB behavior which is also relatively high. Based on these results, to be able to generate a higher frequency of OCB among Denpasar City Land Office employees, the Land Office must be able to support the creation of a better work-life balance for its employees, because a good work-life balance will be able to increase their organizational commitment. This commitment is manifested by loyalty and a strong desire to be able to work for a long time at the Denpasar City Land Office as a return for the comfort felt while working at the Denpasar City Land Office, namely having a good work-life balance, so that employees can relax enough to be able to allocate time in carrying out work and personal activities. High organizational commitment will encourage to be able to bring up a higher frequency of OCB in Denpasar City Land Office employees such as trying to carry out tasks before the deadline and carrying out more tasks than should be done. These results are supported by previous research from Helmy and Pratama (2021); Hartono and Etikariena (2021); and Saputri and Helmy (2021), Eriyanti and Noekent (2021) and Asmony, et al. (2018). The effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment will affect OCB, this means that organizational commitment has a contribution and is able to mediate the influence of work-life balance on OCB.

5. Conclusion

Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on OCB, work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB, and organizational commitment is able to mediate some of the influence between work-life balance on OCB. This research also contributes to the theory of social exchange, namely a good balance between life and work (work-life balance), will have an impact on the reciprocity given by employees to the organization, namely high organizational commitment which also has an impact on OCB displayed by employee at work. Based on these findings, the results of this study are able to enrich the development of human resource management science, especially related to OCB and support the results of other relevant empirical studies regarding the role of work-life balance, organizational commitment to OCB.

The results of the research can be used practically by management as input and considerations related to policy making in an effort to increase the OCB of Denpasar City Land Office employees. The policies owned by the Denpasar City Land Office should be able to consider the balance between work and personal life (work-life balance) of employees. Stakeholders in the Denpasar City Land Office can also innovate regularly from the service aspect, and internal management of employee performance, because these aspects will affect employee organizational commitment to be able to work for a long time, loyalty and feel proud and responsible for being part of the Denpasar City Land Office. High organizational commitment will then have an impact on the work behavior displayed, especially the frequency of work behavior that exceeds the requirements (OCB) displayed will be higher.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript and there no conflict of interest as agreed to the content of this research.

References

- [1] Asmony, T., Nurmayanti, S., & Makiah. (2018). Effect Of Work Life Balance , Workplace Spirituality Of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Through Organizational Commitment As Intervening Variables (Study On Teacher Gen- eration Y In Islamic Boarding School District West Lombok, Indonesia). *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom*, VI (7), pp. 776–800.
- [2] Bustomi, A., Sanusi, I., & Herman (2020). Pengaruh Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Tadbir:Jurnal Manajemen Dakwah*, 5 (1), hal.1-16.
- [3] Blau, P. (1964). *Exchange and Power in Social Life*. New York: Wiley.
- [4] Choi, S. H., & Lee, J. M. (2020). The effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior: the mediating role of psychological safety. *Journal of Digital Convergence*, 18 (3), pp. 83-92.
- [5] Clarke, M. C., Koch, L. C., & Hill, E. J. (2004). The work-family interface: Differentiating balance and fit. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 33(2), pp. 121–140.
- [6] Erdianza, N., Tentama, F., & Sari, E. Y. D. (2020). The effect of work enjoyment and work-life balance on organizational citizenship behavior with job satisfaction as mediator. *International Journal of Management and Humanities*, 4(7), pp. 67-73.
- [7] Eriyanti, H. F., & Noekent, V.(2021). Effect Work-Life Balance on Organizational Commitment: Is The Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior?. *Jurnal Analisis Manajemen*, 10 (4), hal. 376-383.
- [8] Felstead, A., & Henseke, G. (2017). Assessing the growth of remote working and its consequences for effort, well-being and work-life balance. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 32(3), pp. 195–212.
- [9] Fung, N.S., Ahmad, A., and Omar, Z. (2012). Work-Family Enrichment: It's Mediating Role in The Relationship between Dispositional Factors and Job Satisfaction. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Science*, 2(11), pp. 11-88.

- [10] Fiernaningsih, N., Nimran, U., raharjo, K., & Arifin, Z (2019). The role of supervisory support and life balance work in increasing organizational citizenship behavior: Study at hotel employees in Malang. *JPAS (Journal of Public Administration Studies)*, 4(2), pp. 76-84.
- [11] Fisher, G. G., Bulger, C. A., & Smith, C. S. (2009). Beyond work and family: a measure of work/nonwork interference and enhancement. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 14(4), pp. 441-456.
- [12] Ghozali, I. (2021). *Structural Equation Modeling Dengan Metode Alternatif Partial Least Squares (PLS)*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [13] Hair, J., Hult, G., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) (Second Edition)*. Thousand Oaks: SAGE.
- [14] Harikaran, S., & Thevanes, N. (2018). The Relationships among Work-Life Balance , Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Organizational Performance : A Review of Literature. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JMB)*, 20(8), pp. 25–31.
- [15] Heriyadi, Tjahjono, H. K., & Rahayu, M. K. P. (2020). Improving Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Job Satisfaction, Leader-Member Exchange, and Work-Life Balance. *Binus Business Review*. 11(2), hal. 97-104.
- [16] Kim, J-h., Jung, S-h., Seok, B-i., & Choi, H-j. (2022). The Relationship among Four Lifestyles of Workers amid the Covid Pandemic (Work-Life Balance, YOLO, Minimal Life and Staycation) and Organizational Effectiveness: With a Focus on Four Countries. *Journal Sustainability*, 14, 14059, pp. 1-31.
- [17] Lazar, L., Osoian, C., & Ratin, P. (2010). The Role of Work-Life Balance Practice in Order to Improve Organizational Performance. *European Research Studies*. 13(1), pp. 201-214.
- [18] Lavanya, B., & Sree, B. D. Work-life Balance and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour-A study with reference to Bank Employees. *International Research Journal on Advance Science Hub (IRJASH)*, 3(06S), pp. 29-36.
- [19] Lestari, E. R. & Ghaby, N. K. F (2018). Pengaruh Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) terhadap Kepuasan Kerja dan Kinerja Karyawan. *Industria: Jurnal Teknologi dan Manajemen Agroindustri*, 7 (2), hal. 116-123.
- [20] Lingard, H. C., Francis, V., & Turner, M. (2010). Work–family enrichment in the Australian construction industry: Implications for job design. *Construction Management and Economics*, 28(5), pp. 467-480.
- [21] Liu, T., Gao, J., Zhu, M., & Jin, S. (2021). Women's Work-Life Balance in Hospitality: Examining Its Impact on Organizational Commitment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 223, pp. 1-12.
- [22] Luthans, Fred. (2011). *Perilaku organisasi*. Yogyakarta : Andi.
- [23] Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human resource management review*, 1(1), 61-89.
- [24] Nur' Afni, S. A. (2019). The Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Work-life balance on Organizational Citizenship Behavior with Career Development as Mediating Variable (A Case Study at PT. Bank Pembangunan Daerah (BPD) Head Office and Main Branch, Padang). *Atlantis Press: Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 97, pp. 607-618.
- [25] Nurwadi, V., & Ardana, I. (2019). Peran Komitmen Organisasi Dalam Memediasi Pengaruh Organizational Justice Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *E-Jurnal Manajemen*, 8(10), hal. 6219-6241.
- [26] Organ, D. W. (1988). *Organizational citizenship behavior: The good soldier syndrome*. Lexington Books/DC Heath and Com.
- [27] Organ, D.W., Podsakoff, P., & MacKenzie, S. (2006). *Organizations citizenship behavior: Its Nature, antecedents and consequences*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publication.
- [28] Oyewobi, L. O., Oke, A. E., Adeneye, T. D., & Jimoh, R. A. (2019). Influence of organizational commitment on work-life balance and organizational performance of female construction professionals. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 26(10), pp. 2243-2263.
- [29] Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Paine, J. B., & Bachrach, D. G. (2000). Organizational citizenship behaviors: A critical review of the theoretical and empirical literature and suggestions for future research. *Journal of management*, 26(3), pp. 513-563.
- [30] Purwanto, A., Purba, J. T., Bernarto, I., & Sijabat, R. (2021). Effect Of Transformational Leadership, Job Satisfaction, And Organizational Commitments On Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Inovbiz: Journal Inovasi Bisnis*, 9, pp. 61-69.

- [31] Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2022). *Organizational Behavior, Updated 16th Global Edition*. New Jearsey: Pearson Education Limited.
- [32] Rosyadi, H. I., & Bayudhiringantara, M. E. 2021. The Effect Of Flexible Working Arrangements And Social Support On Organizational Commitment With Work-Life Balance As A Mediation Variable. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research*, 5(9), pp. 61-74.
- [33] Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C.M., & Hair, J.F (2017). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. *Handbook of Market Research*, 1-40.
- [34] Setiadi, I. K., & Arieftiara, D. (2022). Mediation role of organizational citizenship behavior Work-Life Balance, Job Embeddedness, and Turnover intention in Islamic Banking. *International Business and Accounting Research Journal*, 6 (1), pp. 1-14.
- [35] Shabir, S., & Gani, A. (2020). Impact Of Work – Life Balance On Organizational Commitment Of Women Health-Care Workers: Structural Modeling Approach. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 28(4), pp. 917-939.
- [36] Shakir, K., & Siddiqui, S. J. (2018). The Relationship Between Work-Life Balance Initiatives and Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Mediating Role of Perceived Organizational Support. *Journal of Independent Studies & Research: Management & Social Sciences & Economics*, 16(2).
- [37] Sylviana, N., Ningsih, R. S. K., Hartati, Y., Yulianti, M., & Satrianto, A. (2020). The Impact of Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment to Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of The Civil Servant (ASN) of Development and Planning Bureau Mentawai Islands Regency. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research (AJHSSR)*. XX, pp. XX-XX.
- [38] Susilawati, E., Amin, S., & Musnaini, M. (2021). Increasing Organizational Citizenship Behavior Through Quality of Work Life and Organizational Commitment. *AFEBI Management and Business Review*, 6(1), pp. 45-58.
- [39] Saraswati, V. A., & Sulistiyo, S. D (2017). The Influence of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment to the Organizational Citizenship Behavior in PT. Haier Sales Indonesia Bandung Branch. *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences* 12 (2). pp. 439-446.
- [40] Suryanatha, A.A.N.B, Sudibya, I.G.A. & Riana, I. G. (2016). Prediktor Organizational Citizenship Behavior Karyawan di The Breezes Bali Resort & Spa Seminyak. *E-Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Udayana*, 5 (12), hal. 4083-4114.
- [41] Talukder, A. K. M. M. H. (2019). Supervisor support and organizational commitment: The role of work–family conflict, job satisfaction, and work–life balance. *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 56(3), pp. 98–116.
- [42] Umar, H. 2011. *Metode Penelitian untuk Skripsi dan Tesis Bisnis Edisi ke-2*. Jakarta: Rajawali Press.
- [43] Wambui, M. L., Cherotich, B. C., Emily, T., & Dave, B. (2017). Effects of Work life balance on Employee Performance in Institutions of Higher Learning. A Case Study of Kabarak University. *Kabarak Journal of Research and Innovation*, 4(2), pp. 60-79.
- [44] Wang, P., & Walumbwa, F.O. (2007). Family-friendly programs, organizational commitment, and work withdrawal: the moderating role of transformational leadership. *Personnel Psychology*, 60(2), pp. 397-427.
- [45] Wilkanandya, U. I., & Sudarma, K. (2020). The Role of Organizational Behavior. *Management Analysis Journal*, 9(3), pp. 300-309.